

THE EFFECT OF CLASSROOM DECORATIONS ON LEARNING CONCENTRATION IN SCIENCE AMONG GRADE IV PUPILS OF SAMAR COLLEGES, INC.: A MIXED-METHOD RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT

Classroom decorations refer to the range of accents placed inside a learning area which provide a visually appealing and engaging environment. This study investigated the effect of classroom decoration to the learning concentration of Grade IV pupils in Science of Samar Colleges, Inc. A mixed-method approach was utilized using explanatory sequential design. Interestingly, the quantitative results of the study revealed that whether a classroom is decorated or not, pupils have a good level of learning concentration. It was also found out that there is no significant difference in the level of learning concentration between students in decorated classrooms and undecorated classrooms. These findings suggest that the physical environment of the classroom may not play a significant influence on the level of learning concentration of Grade IV pupils during their learning activities. The qualitative data suggests that some pupils like decorated classrooms for better learning and interest, but clutter can be distracting; others prefer plain rooms for improved concentration, but some don't see a big difference in their focus either way.

Keywords: *Classroom Decoration, Undecorated Classroom, Learning Concentration, Distraction, Pupil, Grade IV*

INTRODUCTION

The subject classroom decorations have long been an interest and discussion in the field of education. Classrooms have traditionally been decorated with a range of accents in order to provide a visually appealing and engaging learning environment. It is done through posting motivational quotes, educational posters, displaying artworks, and decorating bulletin boards which contains necessary information such as student's status, important announcements, and also the lessons that is needed to be discussed to them. Students' engagement, concentration, behavior, and academic performance can all be strongly impacted by the physical environment in which they learn.

However, the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines has issued Order No. 21, Series of 2023, that is also known as the "No Classroom Decoration" Policy. This is a directive to educational institutions from kindergarten up to the Grade 12 instructing them to remove decorations, posters, and other forms of artwork from classroom walls. "Shall ensure that school grounds, classrooms and all its walls, and other school facilities are clean and free from unnecessary artwork, decorations, tarpaulin, and posters at all times" (DepEd Order No. 21, Series 2023). The directive stipulates that classroom ought to maintain a minimalist appearance, free of any adornments such as posters, decorations, or other affixed materials. Furthermore, classrooms should not be utilized to accumulate goods or store useless objects. This measure aims to reduce distractions that impede students' focus and concentration.

The implementation of such a policy face and underwent many criticisms. Some contend that a deficiency of visual stimulation might result in a bland, dull, and uninspiring learning environment, which may potentially hinder students' creativity and enthusiasm for their studies. Additionally, concerns have been raised about the potential impact on teacher-student interactions, as well as the emotional and psychological well-being of young children who may find a stark and barren classroom less inviting. On the other side, people agreed to the policy that overly-decorated classrooms affect students focus and concentration which makes them distracted during their discussions.

Recent studies have revealed that the way classrooms are arranged and how they look can have a big impact on how children engage and learn in school. Barrett et al. (2015) claimed that the design of a classroom, such as its color, intricacy, and adaptability, can have a real impact on how well students learn, notably in mathematics, reading, and writing. Cleveland and Fisher (2014) also talked about how the physical learning environment can change how students feel and act in class, which can make it harder for them to stay on engaged and motivated. Imms and Byers (2017) also showed that pupils were more focused and emotionally at ease in classrooms that were well-planned. This means that if you decorate the classroom on purpose, it will make pupils feel like they belong and help them focus on the lesson.

The presence of visual stimuli on classroom walls makes it more interesting and stimulating, believed to help and support cognitive development (Smith, 2022). However, in recent years, people have become more interested in the idea of bare or minimalist

classroom walls, which focus on simplicity and cut down on visual clutter (Kwon & Lee, 2021). Proponents of bare walls argue that they reduce distractions and help students pay more attention to the subject matter (McClelland & Reardon, 2023).

A study done by the Association for Psychological Science (2014) has found that the presence of excessive decorations in classrooms might have a negative impact on the attention and learning abilities of young children. The researchers discovered that children in classes with excessive decorations exhibited higher levels of distraction, increased off-task behavior, and had lesser improvements in learning outcomes than when the decorations were eliminated.

Further, Mayer's (2009) Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning proposes that extra information can overload a student's working memory, making it harder for them to learn. This is especially important when too many pictures and illustrations get in the way of the main learning goal. On the other hand, when visual materials are aligned with the lesson, they can help and support cognitive processing and lead to a deeper understanding (Clark & Mayer, 2016).

Similarly, Fisher et. al. (2014) found on his study "The Influence of Classroom Wall Displays on Children's Attention and On-Task Behavior" that well-designed classroom displays that are relevant to the curriculum can positively impact students' attention and on-task behavior, particularly in younger age groups. At the same time, a child psychologist, Dr. Joseph Regalado, has stated that visual aids, including those posted on classroom walls, can be a "big help" in stimulating and reinforcing learning for students, especially young children. He also mentioned that posting students' work on walls may serve as encouragement as it means that their work is being recognized. Therefore, that literature claimed that classroom decoration has a positive impact to student engagement, behavior, and perceptions of the learning environment when done thoughtfully and purposefully.

Despite the anecdotal claims and arguments about this issue, there is a need for a rigorous investigation to provide evidence-based insights into the consequences of posting decorations inside a classroom. This research is conducted to address the following questions: (1) Does the level of pupil's learning concentration differs if the classroom is decorated or undecorated? (2) How does the removal of classroom decorations as mandated by DepEd Order No. 21 affect the level of learning concentration of primary students during academic tasks? and lastly, (3) Are classroom decorations a complete distraction to students in primary grades learning concentration or not?

The main objective of the study conducted is to determine and find out the effect of classroom decoration on the learning concentration in science subject of the Grade IV pupils of Samar Colleges, Inc. Specifically, it aimed to know the following: (1) What is the level of learning concentration of pupils in science under undecorated classroom and decorated classroom? (2) Is there a significant difference between the level of learning concentration in science inside of an undecorated classroom and decorated classroom?

and lastly, (3) What is the perception of the respondents in decorated classroom and undecorated classroom about the effect of the overall classroom environment in their level of learning concentration, and, (4) What does the research findings implies?

The findings in this investigation would help to inform learners, educators, school administrators, and policy makers about the impact of classroom decorations on pupil's learning concentration in science. It is essential for the pupils to be informed and have an understanding of the learning environment's impact on their learning concentration. Furthermore, this study can also help teachers have an idea about how to produce a friendly learning environment for pupils that is essential to their learnings, to identify the only things that should be posted in the classrooms that would also help himself/herself to lessen their task and hustle to clean the classroom and teachers would no longer spend much money from their own pockets just to decorate their classrooms. Another thing, the study would aid school to develop policies regarding the appropriate classroom decorations which may impact the learning outcome of primary students.

After careful consideration, the researcher decided to focus the study on fourth-grade pupils, as this particular age group is situated in a transitional phase between primary and intermediate levels of education. Furthermore, it has been observed that children at this age does require more visual elements to better process the lessons during class discussions. However, they have weak concentration and may be more susceptible to distractions that is why classroom decoration may actually make learning more difficult for them.

The researcher conducted the study in a science class this subject requires more visual aids and materials to make the discussion engaging and enhances understanding to learners. Visual aids such as charts, diagrams, and models help clarify complex concepts, making it easier for students to grasp abstract ideas. The experimental investigation was conducted at Samar Colleges, Inc. Elementary Department, Mabini Avenue, San Roque Street, Catbalogan City, Samar. Moreover, the researchers decided to conduct the research in Samar Colleges, Inc. to further investigate the effect of classroom decorations to the learning concentration of the Grade IV pupils in science of the said institution.

Research Questions

This study sought to investigate the effect of classroom decoration to the learning concentration of Grade IV pupils in Science of Samar Colleges, Inc. Specifically, this aimed to answer the following:

1. What is the level of learning concentration in science of the following pupil-respondents:
 - 1.1. Pupils in decorated classroom
 - 1.2. Pupils in undecorated classroom

2. Is there a significant difference between the level of learning concentration in science of the control group (undecorated classroom) and experimental group (decorated classroom)?

3. What is the perception of the following respondents about the effect of the overall classroom environment in their level of learning concentration:

3.1. Pupils in decorated classroom

3.2. Pupils in undecorated classroom

4. What is the implication of the research findings?

METHODOLOGY

This research study employed mixed-method approach using the explanatory sequential research design. The explanatory sequential design initiates with quantitative data collection and analysis, followed by qualitative data collection and analysis, leading to the interpretation phase. This structured sequence aids in identifying quantitative findings that necessitate additional explanation through qualitative investigation. In particular, the researcher examined if there was a significant difference between the level of learning concentration of the Grade IV pupils in science inside a decorated classroom and undecorated classroom, as well as explored their perceptions of how the overall classroom environment affects their learning concentration.

The respondents of this study were the Grade IV pupils in Samar Colleges, Inc., during the School Year 2023-2024. To identify the respondents for the quantitative phase, a total enumeration sampling was used as sampling procedure where the complete list of Grade IV pupils of Samar Colleges, Inc. was the respondents.

The research study was focused on investigating the effect of classroom decorations on the learning concentration in Science of the Grade IV pupils of Samar Colleges, Inc. The research was limited to Grade IV pupils of Samar Colleges, Inc., as the primary target population. Moreover, it determined their learning concentration in science subject with accordance to the specific types of classrooms they are in, the decorated classroom, which has the presence of educational posters, wall displays, decorated bulletin boards and the like; and the undecorated classroom, which has the complete absence of the things mentioned previously. This was conducted in a science class as this subject matter requires more visual elements and materials to make the discussion engaging and enhances understanding to learners.

This investigation was conducted at Samar Colleges, Inc., Elementary Department, during the School Year 2023-2024. Thus, the findings would not be generalized to other grade levels, class subject, or educational institutions.

For the qualitative phase, a purposive sampling was employed where participants from the initial phase were selected based on specific criteria determined by the responses they provided in the previous phase.

To quantitatively measure and identify the respondents' learning concentration, a researcher-made questionnaire that was given to the participants subsequent to the experiment and observation served as the primary data collection tool.

The whole research questionnaire consisted of only one part. It contains the pupils' personal experience during the experiment that was conducted. It has 25 statements that appraise the level of learning concentration of pupils based on the effects of the experiment conducted. The pupil-respondents' responses were quantified using the five-point Likert scale: 1 for Strongly Disagree (SD), 2 Disagree (D), 3 or Uncertain (U), 4 for Agree (A), 5 for Strongly Agree (SA).

The research also employed structured interviews to identify the participants' perception about the effect of the overall classroom environment in their level of learning concentration. A structured interview is a method of gathering information where questions are asked in a predetermined sequence to gather data on a specific subject (George & Merkus, 2023). With this approach, the researchers prepared, constructed, and organized the questions, and were followed in sequence.

The research study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire to measure the respondents' learning concentration. To guarantee the validity and reliability of the instrument, the researchers prepared the questionnaire for content validation among research experts and Samar Colleges, Inc. Senior High School teacher who were masters in grammar and language, as well as for internal consistency analysis using the Cronbach's Alpha.

The focus of the validation was on the following areas, namely: face, content, and construct validity with consideration on the cognitive and situational perspectives of the pupil-respondents. The suggestions of the experts were considered and were incorporated in the final form that has been reproduced for actual data collection.

Upon assessing the reliability of the instrument using internal consistency, the calculated value of Cronbach's alpha was 0.81, indicating good internal consistency among the items. This suggests that the questionnaire items are correlated with each other, supporting the reliability of the instrument in measuring the level of learning concentration of the pupils.

The conduct of this study was done after the approval by appropriate school authorities that was secured by the researchers. First, the researchers secured a letter to the School Principal of Samar Colleges, Inc. Elementary Department to ask approval to conduct the study on their department with their Grade IV pupils. After the approval was obtained, the researcher formally requested a letter asking permission from the Grade IV Science teacher to allow the researchers to conduct their study during his/her class. Another letter was sent to the class advisers asking permission to allow their classroom to be used for this study. Also, the researcher secured a letter to the participants' parents asking permission for their children to be part of this investigation.

Once all the requests were approved, the researchers proceeded with organizing the classroom settings. There were two separate classrooms needed – one decorated and other undecorated.

After all of that, the participants were exposed to the classroom settings. During the experiment, there was only one teacher who led discussions. To ensure the validity of the study findings, the same science lesson content was discussed to both groups.

On the last day of the experiment, the researcher administered the questionnaire they prepared through a one-on-one interview process where they are the one who read the questionnaire to the pupils and supplied the information based on the pupils' responses, considering that the participants were Grade IV.

Then, this quantitative data was tabulated, computed, analyzed, and interpreted. In accordance with the responses of the pupils in the questionnaire, a new selected set of participants from the experimental group and control group was picked for the interview process, based to the set of criteria. The feedback from the interview provides in-depth and detailed explanation of the data gathered in the quantitative phase. Once finished, the qualitative data then thematically analyzed and interpreted.

After that, both quantitative and qualitative data were integrated to form a conclusion that are grounded with statistical and empirical evidence.

RESULTS

The quantitative and qualitative results obtained from Samar Colleges, Inc.'s Grade IV student respondents are shown in this section. It includes information on how well they learned in both decorated and undecorated classrooms, a statistical comparison of the two groups, and their opinions about how the classroom environment affected their ability to concentrate in class.

Table 1
Level of Learning Concentration of the Pupils-Respondents under Decorated Classroom during the Experiment

Statement	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. I maintain eye contact with the teacher or to the learning material while the discussion is going.	3.84	A
2. I often sit up straight and maintain a forward-leaning posture during the class.	3.95	A
3. I feel alive and not bored inside the classroom environment.	3.74	A

4. I do not yawn and feel sleepy on this kind of set up.	3.16	U
5. I had positive mood and energy level on the entire discussion.	3.37	U
6. I refrain from doing restless behavior in the classroom, such as fidgeting.	2.63	U
7. I finished on-class activities within the allotted time.	3.68	A
8. I complete assignments thoroughly and to the highest standard.	3.84	A
9. I do not consistently ask for repetition.	3.37	U
10. I find the classroom more conducive to my learning.	3.79	A
11. The classroom environment helps me stay attentive and interested in the subject matter.	4.05	A
12. The classroom environment makes me feel more engaged in the learning process.	3.79	A
13. The classroom environment stimulates my interest.	3.84	A
14. The classroom environment contributes to a more pleasant and enjoyable learning atmosphere.	3.68	A
15. The classroom environment helps me listen attentively to my teacher.	3.63	A
16. The classroom environment aided me catch up with the learning process	3.74	A
17. The classroom environment improves my understanding of the subject.	3.63	A
18. The classroom environment helps me think more quickly.	3.53	A
19. The classroom environment helps me respond appropriately and relevantly to other's question.	3.68	A
20. The classroom environment makes it easier for me to understand and remember the information being taught.	3.68	A
21. The classroom environment enhances my focus during lessons.	3.16	U
22. The classroom environment provides me a comfortable place for learning based on the way it was set up.	3.58	A
23. The classroom environment provides me better concentration with the lesson being discussed.	3.58	A
24. The classroom environment does not hinder my focus	3	U

25. Overall, I believe that classroom environment plays a significant role in improving my learning concentration.	3.79	A
Grand Weighted Mean	3.59	
Interpretation	Agree (Good)	

Table 2
Level of Learning Concentration of the Pupils-Respondents under Undecorated Classroom during the Experiment

Statement	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. I maintain eye contact with the teacher or to the learning material while the discussion is going.	4.13	A
2. I often sit up straight and maintain a forward-leaning posture during the class.	4.07	A
3. I feel alive and not bored inside the classroom environment.	4.2	A
4. I do not yawn and feel sleepy on this kind of set up.	3.67	A
5. I had positive mood and energy level on the entire discussion.	3.87	A
6. I refrain from doing restless behavior in the classroom, such as fidgeting.	3.6	A
7. I finished on-class activities within the allotted time.	4.07	A
8. I complete assignments thoroughly and to the highest standard.	3.93	A
9. I do not consistently ask for repetition.	3.33	U
10. I find the classroom more conducive to my learning.	3.87	A
11. The classroom environment helps me stay attentive and interested in the subject matter.	4.2	A
12. The classroom environment makes me feel more engaged in the learning process.	4.33	A
13. The classroom environment stimulates my interest.	3.93	A
14. The classroom environment contributes to a more pleasant and enjoyable learning atmosphere.	4.13	A
15. The classroom environment helps me listen attentively to my teacher.	4.33	A

16. The classroom environment aided me catch up with the learning process	4.2	A
17. The classroom environment improves my understanding of the subject.	3.93	A
18. The classroom environment helps me think more quickly.	3.8	A
19. The classroom environment helps me respond appropriately and relevantly to other's question.	3.67	A
20. The classroom environment makes it easier for me to understand and remember the information being taught.	4	A
21. The classroom environment enhances my focus during lessons.	3.93	A
22. The classroom environment provides me a comfortable place for learning based on the way it was set up.	4.13	A
23. The classroom environment provides me better concentration with the lesson being discussed.	4.27	A
24. The classroom environment does not hinder my focus	3.87	A
25. Overall, I believe that classroom environment plays a significant role in improving my learning concentration.	4.13	A
Grand Weighted Mean	3.98	
Interpretation	Agree (Good)	

Legend:

<u>Range</u>	<u>Interpretation</u>	<u>Meaning</u>
4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Excellent
3.50-4.49	Agree (A)	Good
2.50-3.49	Uncertain (U)	Fair
1.50-2.49	Disagree (D)	Poor
1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Poor

Table 3
Difference between the Level of Learning Concentration of the Experimental Group and Control Group

t-Value	t-Critical	Evaluation/Decision Coefficient
-1.65	2.042	NS / Accept H ₀

$\alpha = 0.050$
df = 30
two-tailed

S = Significant
NS = Not Significant

Table 4
Themes

General Questions	Specific Questions	Codes	Themes
1. What is the perception of the pupil-respondents about the effect of the overall classroom environment in their learning concentration?	1.1. What is the perception of the pupils in decorated classroom?	Distracted	Pupil-respondents' perception of the effect of classroom environment to their learning concentration
		Enhances focus	
		Improve mood	
		Not boring	
		Give motivation	
		Help generate ideas	
	1.2. What is the perception of the pupils in undecorated classroom?	Can't think straight	
		Less distraction	
		Uninviting	
		Boring	
		Simple	
		Decoration is for kindergarten	
		Environment doesn't affect them	
		It doesn't affect learning	
Clean and organize			

DISCUSSION

Pupils in decorated classroom. Table 1 shows that, out of 25 statements, the experimental group "agreed" on 19 of them and was "uncertain" about the other 6 with the weighted means ranged from 2.63 to 4.05. The statement that had the greatest and lowest weighted averages in this set of statements were "I refrain from doing restless behavior in the classroom, such as fidgeting," and "the classroom environment helps me stay attentive and interested in the subject matter."

The grand weighted mean of 3.59 indicates that, overall, the respondents "agreed" on the level of learning concentration during the experiment. This meant that they have "good" level of learning concentration with the classroom being adorned as opposed to being empty. The experimental group implied that having decorations in the classroom improves their ability to concentrate. This is in line with what research has shown: that the right visual displays can make learning more interesting, especially for younger students who learn better with visual aids (Fisher et al., 2014). McClelland and Reardon (2023) also said that well-designed learning spaces can affect emotional motivation and focus, especially when the decorations are related to the material being taught.

Pupils in undecorated classroom. It can be gleaned on Table 2 that of the 25 statements, the control group "agreed" on 24 statements, while they were "uncertain" on the remaining one with weighted means ranging from 3.33 to 4.33. In these statements, the statements stating, "the classroom environment makes me feel more engaged in the learning process" also "the classroom environment helps me listen attentively to my teacher," and "I do not consistently ask for repetition" were rated with the highest and least weighted means, respectively.

Taken as a whole, the pupil-respondents "agreed" on the level of learning concentration during the experiment being supported by the grand weighted mean of 3.98. This signified that they have "good" level of learning concentration inside a classroom being undecorated rather than it being decorated. Impliedly, the control group expressed that they have better learning concentration with the classroom having its plain appearance, without the presence of any decorations. This finding backs up earlier research that found that too many visual stimuli can be distracting and make it hard for students to concentrate (Fisher et al., 2014; Association for Psychological Science, 2014). Mayer's (2009) Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning also says that extra visuals can overload working memory, which makes learning less effective.

Difference between the Level of Learning Concentration of the Experimental Group and Control Group. Table 3 presents the difference between the level of learning concentration of the experimental group which are the pupil-respondent exposed to decorated classroom, and the control group which are the pupil-respondent under undecorated classroom.

It can be noted from the table that looking into the linear association between the level of learning concentration of pupils inside a decorated classroom and pupils under an undecorated classroom, there is no statistically significant difference. The t-test results

comparing the level of learning concentration between students in decorated and undecorated classrooms yield a t-value of -1.65, with a t-critical of 2.042 at a significance level of 0.05 for a two-tailed test, and degrees of freedom (df) equal to 30. So, this means that there was no statistical difference observed between the two groups, as the absolute value of the t-value is less than the t-critical which fails to reject the null hypothesis. This implies that classroom decoration may not significantly influence students' concentration levels during learning activities, at least within the parameters of this study and with the sample size provided. Kwon and Lee (2021) found similar results, saying that the overall effect of visual stimuli on academic performance can vary a lot depending on the student's age, the situation, and the type of content being taught in the classroom. Some students do better in environments with a lot of visual stimulation, while others do better in simple and bare ones. Also, Barrett et al.'s (2015) meta-analysis found that classroom's design, such as the lighting, color, and organization, affects how well students learn, but it is not the only thing that affects their focus or performance.

Perception of the Pupil-respondents about the Effect of the Overall Classroom Environment in their Learning Concentration

Research Question 1: What is the perception of the pupils in decorated classroom about the effect of the overall classroom environment in their level of learning concentration?

P1: *"I prefer a classroom with decorations, but it makes me distracted sometimes".*

Interpretation: The pupil-respondent like it more when the classroom has a decoration as he finds it very helpful. But he/she sometimes gets distracted by it. When the decorations are too much, it really hinders his/her concentration with to the lesson. However, the designs and poster posted inside the classroom helps him/her to learn because it is related to their discussion.

P2: *"I want a decorated classroom; I like the designs inside but it distracts me sometimes".*

Interpretation: The pupil-respondent find classroom decorations visually appealing and engaging. However, there is sometimes when he/she got distracted by it. In short, decorations made the classroom very beautiful and exciting that it made him/her inspired and motivated, but it also prevents him/her to stay focus on the lesson.

P3: *"I rather have a colorful classroom in my opinion because its happier unlike the plain one. It makes me more excited to learn because its happy and I'm not bored unlike the other day and month it was boring, now my learning leveled up".*

Interpretation: The pupil-respondent prefer to have a classroom with the presence of decoration because it gives him/her positive vibe. Because of the designs, the pupil gets motivated and inspired to learn. He/she find a plain classroom boring, dull, and no life. All in all, he/she finds the decoration a big help on his/her learning.

P4: "Decorations is 100 out of 10 for me. I would like a colorful classroom that is fun to look at. The decorations made me more interested and focus on class."

Interpretation: The pupil-respondent prefer the classroom decorated because it made him/her fun and entertaining. This type of classroom improved his/her learning concentration, plus it makes him be enthusiastic. Based on the rating he/she gives, he/she extremely favored a classroom with decorations.

P5: "I like colorful rooms; it helps me get idea from those decorations".

Interpretation: The pupil-respondent perception of a classroom where a lot of colors and decorations can be seen, it boosts his/her mind in formulating ideas. The designs help the pupil a lot because he/she can think properly with the presence of it. By looking at the decorations, it somehow gives and help him/her to generate and produce an idea to answer.

P6: "I like more colorful, more decorations inside the classroom, it helps me learn, especially the topics that are posted on the walls".

Interpretation: The pupil-respondent prefer a classroom with a colorful environment. The more decorations can be seen, the more he/she finds it inviting. He/she also finds the lessons posted on the wall a helpful for his/her learning. It aids and guide him/her with the discussion being taught by their teacher.

P7: "A classroom which has a few topics of the subjects we are gonna learn. I like classroom with decorations."

Interpretation: The pupil-respondent favor a decorated classroom where topics that will going to be discussed is posted inside it. He/she believes that he/she will learn more with the presence of it. He/she can have some new hints and overview the lessons due to the fact that topics are posted in the walls of the classroom.

P8: "I want the normal and plain classroom, I can't think straight because of the designs".

Interpretation: The pupil-respondent prefer the clean, minimalist, and plain classroom. He/she finds the decorations distracting. The classroom with too many decorations hinders him/her to think properly and process ideas because of the posters and designs around them. The classroom without designs is much better for him/her.

Research Question 2: What is the perception of the pupils in undecorated classroom about the effect of the overall classroom environment in their level of learning concentration?

P1: "I like to have decorations because a classroom with a decoration motivates me in all subjects and I can focus more on the lesson".

Interpretation: The pupil-respondents don't like the plain classroom. He/she wants it to be filled with decorations because he/she believes that those decorations motivate him/her to learn more in their class. He/she also think that he/she can concentrate more in the discussions if the classroom is decorated suggesting only that he/she finds undecorated classroom boring less exciting.

P2: "I like decoration that improve the atmosphere of the classroom".

Interpretation: The pupil-respondent find the undecorated classroom dull and uninviting. He/she believes that by placing decorations inside, it can greatly change the atmosphere inside the classroom making it more positive, happier, and interesting.

P3: "I want it with decoration but not over decorated because no decoration is boring".

Interpretation: The pupil-respondents suggests that classroom should have well-managed decorations because with decorations, he/she finds it more welcoming, comfortable, and friendly. But he/she doesn't want it to be overly decorated as well because it might get him/her distracted. He/she want the area to have a simple decoration because a complete absence of ornaments makes him/her bored.

P4: "I prefer a plain classroom than a classroom with an excessive decoration because it is simple".

Interpretation: The pupil-respondent favor a classroom with no decorations because he/she finds it simple, minimalist, and friendly to his/her learning concentration.

P5: "I want something simple and not flashy since I am not a kindergarten. But it's good for visual learners, just not for me".

Interpretation: The pupil-respondent desire a simple classroom because seeing colorful things posted on his/her environment is not appealing for him/her. Being inside a classroom with full of decorations gives him/her a vibe of a kindergarten. However, he/she believes that decorated classroom may be beneficial to others, but not for him/her.

P6: "I like it plainer, clean, and organized classroom just like now".

Interpretation: The pupil-respondent prefer the classroom plainer with clean look and less decorations because when the classroom is unorganized it distracts his/her attention. Too many designs posted bother him/her.

P7: "The decorations don't disturb me at all but I just prefer how our classroom looks like".

Interpretation: The pupil-respondents suggests that he/she is fine how their classroom is currently being set up. He/she is okay with it being plain and simple. But he/she is also fine if the classroom has decoration. All in all, whether the classroom is decorated or undecorated, it doesn't matter to him/her.

P8: "The classrooms don't have an impact to my learning concentration".

Interpretation: The pupil-respondent perception about the learning concentration is that it doesn't get affected by his/her visual environment. The researcher perceives it like the pupil is suggesting that he/she is fine no matter how their classroom looks like.

Implication of the Findings of the Study

The following were the implications derived from the findings of the study:

1. Even with the presence of different visual elements, pupils inside a decorated classroom have a "good" level of learning concentration.

2. Despite the bare appearance of the classroom, pupils inside in an undecorated classroom has a "good" level of learning concentration.

3. There is no significant difference between the level of learning concentration of pupils inside a decorated classroom and undecorated classroom which implies that classroom decoration may not significantly influence pupils' concentration levels during learning activities, at least within the parameters of this study and with the sample size provided.

4. The pupils inside a decorated classroom expressed the preference on how their classroom is set-up as it helps to maintain their focus, boost their interest, and enhance their understanding of the lessons. However, if decorations are not managed well, it impedes their concentration.

5. The pupils inside in an undecorated classroom suggests that they experience better concentration with this set-up. They find that without various adornment, they can focus better, and nothings is grabbing away their attention. But some as well indicated that whether classroom is decorated or not, there is no difference at all.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. While statistical analysis revealed no significant overall difference and disparities between decorated and undecorated classroom, pupils feedback highlights the importance of individual preferences and tolerance levels for visual stimulation. This suggests that the effect of classroom decorations on learning concentration cannot be universally. Some students feel they can focus better without decorations, while others don't think it makes much of a difference either way. Thus, it becomes evident that classroom decorations have no one-size-fits-all effect on learning concentration, emphasizing that it can be different for each person.

2. It is evident that the decoration can contribute to the learning environment. When used effectively, decorations can provide visual support, create a welcoming atmosphere, and increase motivation among learners. However, when the decorations are excessive, they can instead become a source of distraction for many pupils. It is crucial for decorations to be purposeful and well-managed in order to be effective. They can help reinforce important concepts and make the space more engaging. It is important to strike a balance when it comes to decorating classrooms. If decorations are too excessive or unrelated to the lessons being taught, they can actually become a source of distraction for many pupils.

3. Students benefit the most from decorations that are directly related to the lessons being taught or that provide visual cues to help with learning. This points to the importance of teachers focusing on the strategic views of decorations rather than simply filling up space. By focusing on purposeful and well-managed decorations, teachers can create a more conducive learning environment for their students, enhancing the overall educational experience.

4. Factors such as age and learning style should be considered when setting up a classroom. Some responses suggest that younger pupils may benefit more from colorful environments, while others believe that simplicity is better for maintaining focus at any age. This discrepancy highlights the need for further investigations to understand how age and learning style affect what kind of classroom setup works best for different student.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn from the findings of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. When it comes to decorating classroom, it is important incorporating student choice and flexibility. Students should be empowered to have some level of control over the decorations and the learning environment. This can be achieved by providing designated spaces for students to showcase their own work or contributions to classroom displays. Additionally, allowing students to select or contribute to some of the decorative

elements can be beneficial, with focus on relevance to the subject matter. Also, it is also important to be open to temporarily removing certain decorations if they become a distraction during activities that require deep focus.

2. Another key aspect to make decorations as a teaching tool, rather than “simply filling the walls.” Consider posting decorations that is directly connected to lessons which could aid learning, such as posters with key vocabulary, formulas, or visual explanations of concepts.

3. Create a home or calm zone within the classroom. This designated area should have minimal visual stimulation for pupils who may feel overwhelmed by excessive decoration. Students should have the option to work or take breaks in this zone.

4. Furthermore, collaborating with learners is crucial in maintaining an effective classroom environment. Regular feedback from pupils about the decorations can provide valuable insights. Are certain decorations distracting or helpful? Are their areas that feel too sparse or too visually busy? This feedback can help in creating a space that is conducive to learning.

5. Maintain a well-organized space, regardless of the level of decoration. A clutter-free and visually organized classroom capsule the promoting focus and productivity. A chaotic environment is distracting for most learners, so clear structure and designated places for materials are essential components of a conducive learning area.

6. Lastly, further research should delve deeper to discover why some pupils thrive in a decorated classroom, while others are distracted. This investigation could explore the potential influence of age, personality traits, and specific learning styles on pupils' responses to classroom decorations. Also, a study where the degree of decoration is carefully controlled, such as distinguishing between subject-related and purely aesthetic decorations, might yield clearer results about the impact on learning concentration.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this mixed-method research, the researchers recognized the ethical considerations related to confidentiality and privacy and concerns regarding reproducibility and research quality. To address these considerations, the researchers utilized a questionnaire and structured interview as a primary data collection method. Prior to data gathering, the researchers placed great emphasis on the validation and reliability analysis of the questionnaire and the interview questions. Through face, content, and construct validation, they engaged experts in the field to carefully review and validate the questionnaire and the interview questions, ensuring their relevance and appropriateness for the study. This process contributed to the ethical integrity of the research, as it allowed the researchers to gather meaningful data while maintaining the participants' right and dignity.

Additionally, before they answered the questionnaire and participate in the structured interview, the researcher ensured that the pupil-respondents fully understand

the purpose of the study, and that they are wholeheartedly willing to participate in the investigation by obtaining informed consent from the pupils and their parents or guardians. Clear instructions are provided, and participants are made aware of their rights, including their privacy protections and the prevention of the disclosure of private and sensitive information. The whole data gathering process was conducted in a respectful and non-coercive manner, with sensitivity to the participants' feelings and perspectives. Researchers ensured that any information disclosed during the process is kept confidential and will be used only for this research.

By integrating these ethical considerations into the research methodology, the researchers aided to enhance the overall methodological rigor and credibility of their mixed-method investigation. This approach facilitated the ethical treatment of the participants, protected their confidentiality and privacy, and increased the potential for research replication and validity.

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